

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some 6-*p*-Tolyl-7*H*-indeno[2,1-*c*]quinolines

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Manuscript received 26 October 1988, revised 27 January 1989, accepted 31 March 1989

6-*p*-Tolyl-7*H*-indeno[2,1-*c*]quinolines (4a-e) have been synthesised by the condensation of 2-(4'-methyl)benzoylindan-1,3-dione (1) with appropriately substituted anilines followed by cyclodehydration with polyphosphoric acid and Wolff-Kishner reduction. The compounds have been characterised by their analytical and spectral data. The compounds 3a-e have been shown to possess noticeable antiinflammatory activity.

AZFLUORENES and their benzanalogues (indenoquinolines) are reported to possess varied biological activity¹⁻³. Recently, some indenoquinolines were reported to exhibit significant analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity⁴. In view of these reports and in continuation of our work⁵, we report here the synthesis of some new 6-*p*-tolyl-7*H*-indeno[2,1-*c*]quinolines (Scheme 1).

Results and Discussion

2-(4'-Methyl)benzoylindan-1,3-dione (1)⁶ upon refluxing with anilines in EtOH for 3 h gave the corresponding anils (2a-e) in excellent yields. The ir spectra of the anils exhibited ir bands at 1695-1685 (C=O, in a five-membered ring) and 1640-1630 cm⁻¹ (C=N), and their pmr spectra revealed the presence of enolic OH (δ 12.48-12.40, exchangeable with D₂O).

The anils on treatment with PPA at 180° for 30 min yielded cyclised ketones (3a-e; $\nu_{\max}$ 1715-1700 cm⁻¹). The most prominent feature of the ketones (3a-e) is that H-1 and H-11 appeared downfield at δ 8.30-8.44. This significant deshielding of the protons is attributed to steric interaction. The most downfield signal has been assigned to H-1. Similarly situated proton in 7*H*-benzo[*c*]fluorenone⁷ has been reported to be more deshielded than H-11. This fact is further supported from the pmr spectra of the ketones 3b and 3c which exhibited one-proton doublet at δ 8.44 (*J* 2.5 Hz) and 8.35 (*J* 8 Hz), respectively, attributed to H-1.

The ketones (3a-e) on Wolff-Kishner reduction afforded the desired indenoquinolines. These compounds did not display any absorption in the carbonyl region and exhibited two-proton singlets at δ 4.15, ascribable to C(7)-H₂ protons. H-1

- 2-4 a ; R₁=R₂=R₃=H
 b ; R₁=OH, R₂=R₃=H
 c ; R₂=OH, R₁=R₃=H
 d ; R₃=OH, R₁=R₂=H
 e ; R₂=NO₂, R₁=R₃=H

Scheme 1

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND PMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUND 2-4*

Compd. no.	M p. °C	Yield %	R _f × 100	Mol formula	δ (ppm)
2a	200	85	57	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	2.40 (3H, s, CH ₃ -4'), 6.75-6.95 (2H m, H-2', H-6') 7.05-7.40 (7H, m, ArH), 7.50-7.85 (4H, m indane), 12.45 (1H, br, H-3, exchangeable with D ₂ O)
2b	192	80	56	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	2.21 (3H, s, CH ₃ -4'), 2.40 (3H, s, OH ₂ -4''), 6.70 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 6.95 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, H-3', H-5'), 7.20 (4H, m, ArH), 7.50-7.85 (4H, m, indane), 12.40 (1H, br, H-3, exchangeable)
2c	180	80	59	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	2.20 (3H, s, CH ₃ -3'), 2.40 (3H, s, CH ₃ -4''), 6.50-7.05 (4H, m, ArH), 7.10-7.40 (4H, m, ArH), 7.50-7.80 (4H, m, indane), 12.40 (1H, H-3, exchangeable)
2d	178	85	58	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	2.33 (s, OH ₂ -2'), 2.40 (CH ₃ -4''), 6.60 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-6'), 6.85 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-4'), 6.95 (2H, m, H-3', H-5'), 7.10-7.40 (4H m, ArH), 7.50-7.80 (4H, m, indane), 12.40 (1H, br, H-3, exchangeable)
2e	220	75	53	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₂	2.38 (3H, s, CH ₃ -4'), 6.78-7.88 (12H, m, ArH), 12.48 (1H, br, H-3, enolic)
3a	260	80	63	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ON	2.45 (3H, s, CH ₃ -4'), 7.00-7.45 (4H, m, ArH), 7.50-7.80 (5H, m, H-2', H-6', H-8, H-9, H-10), 8.30 (2H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-4, H-11), 8.44 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-1)
3b	280	70	60	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ON	2.45 (3H, s, CH ₃ -4'), 2.57 (3H, s, OH ₂ -2), 7.30-8.25 (11H, m) 8.44 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-1)
3c	217	76	62	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ON	2.45 (3H, s, CH ₃ -4'), 2.55 (3H, s, OH ₂ -3), 7.20-7.85 (8H, m), 7.75 (1H, br, W _{1/2} 5 Hz, H-4), 8.05 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-11) 8.35 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-1)
3d	240	80	63	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ ON	2.45 (3H, s, CH ₃ -4'), 2.83 (3H, s, OH ₂ -4), 7.30-7.80 (7H, m), 7.95 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 8.15 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-11), 8.40 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-1)
3e	252	62	57	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	2.42 (3H, s, CH ₃ -4'), 7.10-8.35 (10H, m, ArH), 8.45 (1H, dd, J 8 Hz and 2.5 Hz, H-1)
4a	138	64	66	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N	2.45 (3H, s, CH ₃ -4'), 4.15 (2H, s, OH ₂), 7.10-7.95 (9H, m), 8.25 (2H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-4, H-11), 8.50 (1H, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-1)
4b	146	64	65	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N	2.4 (3H, s, CH ₃ -4'), 2.63 (3H, s, CH ₃ -3), 4.15 (2H, s, OH ₂), 7.30 (1H, J 8 Hz, H-3), 7.40-7.80 (5H, m), 7.85 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, H-2, H-2', H-6'), 8.15 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-4), 8.42 (2H, br, H-1, H-11)
4c	180	70	64	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N	2.45 (3H, s, CH ₃ -4'), 2.55 (3H, s, CH ₃ -3), 4.15 (2H, s, OH ₂), 7.20-7.60 (6H, m), 7.95 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 8.05 (br, W _{1/2} 5 Hz, H-4), 8.30 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-11), 8.50 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-1)
4d	150	65	67	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N	2.45 (3H, s, CH ₃ -4'), 2.83 (3H, s, OH ₂ -4), 4.15 (2H, s, OH ₂), 7.20-7.80 (7H, m), 7.95 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 8.05-8.35 (2H, dd, J 8 Hz and 2.5 Hz, H-1, H-11)
4e	162	60	63	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂	2.45 (3H, s, CH ₃ -4'), 4.18 (2H, s, OH ₂), 7.15-8.32 (10H, m, ArH), 8.52 (1H, dd, J 8 Hz and 2.5 Hz, H-1)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

and H-11 protons appeared downfield at δ 8.05-8.50.

Biological activity: Compounds 3a-e were screened for their general pharmacological activity, LD₅₀ of the compounds were found to be >1000 mg/kg. These compounds did not show any significant CNS and CVS activity in gross observation test. However, compounds 3a-e showed noticeable anti-inflammatory activity (30, 35, 33, 31 and 28% inhibition, respectively at a dose level of 100 mg/kg) as compared with phenylbutazone (62% inhibition). This activity was tested by carragenin induced rat paw oedema test⁹.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectro-

photometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Solvent system used for tlc was benzene-ethyl acetate (8 : 2).

α-(1,3-Dioxindan-2-yl)-4'-methylbenzylindeneanilines (2): A mixture of 2-(4'-methyl)benzoylindan-1,3-dione (1; 0.001 mol) and freshly distilled anilines (0.0013 mol) was refluxed in absolute ethanol (30 ml) for 3 h in presence of a few drops of acetic acid. The solvent was then distilled off and the residue crystallised from ethanol to yield green needles of 2a-e (Table 1).

6-p-Tolyindene[2,1-c]quinoline-7H-7-ones (3a-e): The anils (2; 1 g) were added to freshly prepared PPA and heated to 180° for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then decomposed by pouring it over ice-cold water. The aqueous layer was made alkaline by NH₄OH and the resulting solids were filtered,

washed with water and crystallised from benzene to yield shining yellow needles of 3a-e (Table 1).

6-p-Tolyl-7H-indeno[2,1-c]quinoline (4a-e): A mixture of the ketones (3; 0.001 mol), ethylene glycol (9 ml), hydrazine hydrate (2.5 ml) and KOH (0.2 g) was heated to 120° for 1 h and then at 180° for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice-cold water and the resulting solids were filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from MeOH-C₅H₅N to furnish colourless needles of 4a-e (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Kurukshetra, Kurukshetra,

for ir and pmr spectra and C.D.R.I, Lucknow for biological screening of the compounds.

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